

Seagrass Sentinel: Technical Methodology

Version 1.1, February 2026

Overview

The Seagrass Sentinel is a cloud-native Earth Observation application designed to monitor submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV) dynamics and coastal water quality stressors. The tool uses the Google Earth Engine (GEE) API for server-side processing, using multi-sensor fusion to address common limitations in optical remote sensing of benthic habitats.

1. Data Acquisition & Pre-Processing

Optical Imagery: The system processes Sentinel-2 MSI (Level-2A) surface reflectance data.

Cloud Masking: A QA60 bitmask is used to eliminate opaque clouds and cirrus.

Water Masking: A dynamic water mask is created using the Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI) to delineate the marine area and minimise processing load on terrestrial pixels.

Depth Correction (Lyzenga): To account for water column attenuation, we use a Lyzenga water column correction (Lyzenga, 1978; 1981). Deep-water radiometric calibration is dynamically performed based on the user's Region of Interest (ROI) to linearise the relationship between bottom reflectance and depth.

2. Classification Algorithm

Model: A Random Forest (RF) supervised classifier (Breiman, 2001) is trained in real-time.

Training Data: Ground truth training points are obtained from the UNEP-WCMC Global Distribution of Seagrasses dataset (UNEP-WCMC, Short, 2021).

Validation and Accuracy Assessment: To ensure scientific rigour and prevent model overfitting, the extracted in situ coordinates undergo a randomised 70/30 train-test split within the user-defined Region of Interest (ROI). The RF model is trained solely on 70% of the localised dataset. The remaining 30% is withheld to perform an independent accuracy assessment. The platform automatically generates a confusion matrix and reports the Overall Accuracy (OA) and Cohen's Kappa coefficient (Cohen, 1960; Congalton, 1991) for both the baseline and current temporal observation windows.

Feature Space: The classifier inputs include Sentinel-2 spectral bands (B2, B3, B4), the Depth-Invariant Index (DII), and derived turbidity indices.

Class Output: The model classifies pixels into distinct categories: Seagrass Present, Seagrass Absent (Sand/Substrate), and Deep Water.

3. Environmental Stressor Detection

Turbidity: Suspended Sediment Concentration (SSC) proxies are determined using red-edge spectral algorithms to identify turbidity plumes that restrict photosynthetically active radiation (PAR).

Thermal Stress: Sea Surface Temperature (SST) is calculated using thermal bands from Landsat 8 (TIRS) and Landsat 9 (TIRS-2). A threshold of $>23.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ is used to identify potential thermal-stress areas for temperate seagrass species (USGS, 2024).

4. Change Detection

The application measures the net change in benthic cover between two user-defined time periods (Period A versus Period B). Post-classification comparison (PCC) is utilised to quantify specific transitions (e.g., Stable Seagrass, Loss, Gain).

Citation

Farrugia, J., & The Oceans Need Us. (2026). Seagrass Sentinel: Technical Methodology (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18711452>

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Algorithms and Methods

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